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Editor: Ivan Spasojević

Technical support: Dragana Robajac

Cover design: Zoran Beloševac

Publisher: Faculty of Chemistry, Serbian Biochemical Society

Printed by: Colorgrafx, Belgrade

Serbian Biochemical Society

Tenth Conference

with international participation

24.09.2021. Kragujevac, Serbia

“Biochemical Insights into Molecular Mechanisms”

Levothyroxine: biochemical aspects and consumption in Serbia

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Thyroid hormones play a vital role in the regulation of numerous metabolic processes and they are essential for normal growth and development. The thyroid gland produces, stores and releases iodine-containing hormones thyroxine (T₄) and triiodothyronine (T₃). The predominant hormone produced by the thyroid gland is T₄, with approximately 70–90 µg of T₄ and 15–30 µg of T₃ produced daily. They make certain effects by entering the cell nucleus and binding to DNA-bound thyroid receptors, which regulate gene transcription and synthesis of proteins involved in metabolism of proteins, carbohydrates and lipids. Tissue-specific modulation of the thyroid hormone activity depends on thyroid hormone secretion, plasma transport, transmembrane transport, activation/inactivation, and interaction with nuclear receptor isoforms and their co-regulators. Naturally, the hormones secreted by the thyroid are regulated by the hypothalamic–pituitary–thyroid axis through a negative feedback system¹. Inadequate or decreased synthesis of any of these hormones requires appropriate replacement treatment. Hypothyroidism is one of the most common endocrine disorders and diagnosis is based on statistical reference ranges of the relevant biochemical parameters (thyroxine and TSH level). Levothyroxine is synthetic thyroxine hormone that is biochemically and physiologically indistinguishable from the natural form produced normally in body. It is commonly used for treatment of primary (thyroidal), secondary (pituitary) and tertiary (hypothalamic) hypothyroidism, as well as for euthyroid goiters including thyroid nodules, subacute or chronic lymphocytic thyroiditis, multinodular goiter or for thyroid cancer patients who have undergone thyroidectomy. Biochemical findings of subclinical hypothyroidism can be found in asymptomatic population¹. According to data obtained from website for Medicines and Medical Devices Agency of Serbia for 2009 and 2019, it is noticed remarkable change in average annual consumption of approved levothyroxine medicines (doses per tablet 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, and 150 µg). An increasing trend in the number of people that need thyroxine replacement is evident. To facilitate the ability to compare consumption information between countries a defined daily dose (DDD) is introduced. It represents “the assumed

average maintenance dose per day for a drug used for its main indication in adults". This parameter is fixed unit of measurement independent of price, currencies, pack size and strength, enabling trends in drug utilization to be assessed and compared between population group in different countries. In 2009, total annual consumption of levothyroxine-sodium was 6.19 DDD/1000 inhabitants/day, and in 2019, it was 19.26 DDD/1000 inhabitants/day. This indicates growing population with diagnosed thyroid deficiency and increased consumption of hormone replacement in therapy ^{2,3}.

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